

The ISARIC Anti-Stigma Guidelines

**A toolkit for stigma mitigation in
infectious disease outbreaks**

Collaboratively developed by the International Severe Acute Respiratory and Emerging Infection Consortium (ISARIC), University of Oxford's Pandemic Sciences Institute (PSI), and Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network (GOARN)

Executive Summary

The ISARIC Anti-Stigma Guidelines are a practical resource collaboratively developed by outbreak responders, stigma researchers, and people with relevant lived experience to guide outbreak response organisations in identifying and mitigating stigma during infectious disease outbreaks. Stigma is a recurring, harmful feature of outbreaks that undermines public health responses and exacerbates social inequality. Despite growing awareness of these harms, operational guidance for outbreak-related stigma reduction remains limited.

These guidelines address that gap through two core components:

1. Guiding Principles for Stigma-Sensitive Outbreak Management

Grounded in human rights and ethical public health practice, these principles are relevant to all outbreak responders. There are nine principles that span communication, governance, and service delivery. Good practice indicators are provided alongside the principles to guide and evaluate implementation.

2. Recommended Interventions to Reduce Outbreak-Related Stigma

A range of expert-endorsed, evidence-based interventions to reduce stigma are provided. These are categorised by outbreak phase (preparedness, response, recovery) and address four stigma sub-domains: social, structural, provider/authority-related, and self stigma. Each is supported by an evidence summary, strength of recommendation from the expert panel, and implementation guidance.

The guideline were developed through a robust process combining systematic review, stakeholder interviews across all WHO regions, community surveys in three outbreak contexts (mpox, Ebola disease, and Nipah virus disease), and extensive expert consultation. The guideline reflect best-available insights and are designed to be adaptable across diverse outbreak settings.

Stigma-sensitive outbreak response improves trust, equity, and effectiveness. This guidelines offers concrete starting points for outbreak response actors to avoid harm and actively support those affected.

ISARIC Anti-Stigma Guiding Principles

Communication and knowledge exchange

1. All health communication should reflect the humanity and dignity of affected populations.	This principle reflects an understanding that language can shape perceptions and behaviours and contribute to empathy or stigma.
2. Messaging should not imply that specific groups are responsible for the outbreak.	Outbreaks result from a complex combination of factors, not the actions of any specific group. Messaging that implies blame or portrays disease as innately linked to a particular population can exacerbate discrimination.
3. Outbreak communication mechanisms should be designed for two-way engagement with communities.	Effective communication that involves discussion rather than unidirectional instruction can help ensure community concerns are addressed and messaging is contextually-sensitive.

Policy and governance

4. Affected communities should be meaningfully engaged in decisions that impact them.	Affected communities should have a voice in the actions that influence their wellbeing. This involvement also helps to design more effective and appropriate interventions.
5. Outbreak response institutions should model the inclusive and transparent behaviours they promote.	Institutional trustworthiness is a prerequisite for building lasting community trust. Stigma needs to be addressed within institutions before it can be effectively addressed externally.
6. The effectiveness and adverse effects of outbreak control measures and stigma reduction interventions should be assessed and transparently reported.	Evaluating and documenting stigma-related outcomes enables shared learning and strengthens accountability in outbreak response.

Service design and delivery

7. Outbreak services should be designed to minimise dehumanisation and alienation.	Service environments that undermine privacy, use othering terminology, or treat individuals disrespectfully can reinforce stigma and deepen social exclusion.
8. Outbreak measures should be evidence-based and no more restrictive than necessary to minimise social disruption.	Introducing outbreak measures that are excessively restrictive and/or not rooted in evidence may cause unnecessary social division and erode public trust, predisposing to stigma.
9. Psychosocial support should be accessible to affected populations and frontline workers as part of outbreak management.	Psychosocial and social wellbeing is a critical component of health and plays an important role in reducing the occurrence and internalisation of stigma.

Recommended Stigma Reduction Interventions

Preparedness

A1			
A2			
A3			
A4			
A5			
A6			

Response

B1			
B2			
B3			
B4			
B5			
B6			
B7			

Recovery

C1			
C2			
C3			
C4			
C5			

Keys

Strength of recommendations:

- **Strong recommendation for intervention**
- **Conditional recommendation for intervention**
- **Support for use in further research only**
- **Conditional recommendation against intervention**
- **Strong recommendation against intervention**

Stigma sub-domains:

- **Social stigma**
- **Provider/authority-related stigma**
- **Structural stigma**
- **Self stigma**

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
ISARIC Anti-Stigma Guiding Principles	2
Recommended Stigma Reduction Interventions.....	3
Abbreviations	6
Glossary of Key Terms	7
Introduction to the Guidelines	8
Background.....	8
Objectives.....	9
Target audience	9
Scope of guidance.....	10
Structure and key components.....	11
Development process	12
Part A: ISARIC Guiding Principles for Stigma-Sensitive Outbreak Response	13
Overview of the guiding principles	13
i. Communication and knowledge exchange principles	14
ii. Policy and governance principles.....	17
iii. Service design and delivery principles	20
Part B: Recommended Stigma Reduction Interventions	23
Overview of the stigma reduction interventions.....	23
Section A: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak <i>preparedness</i>	26
Section B: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak <i>response</i>	32
Section C: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak <i>recovery</i>	39
Concluding Remarks	45
Guideline Contributors	46
Funding	48
ISARIC Anti-stigma Guiding Principles and Good Practice Indicators Checklist	49
References	52

Abbreviations

AMSTAR	A MeaSurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews
CERQual	Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative Research
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
GOARN	Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network
GRADE	Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ISARIC	International Severe Acute Respiratory and Emerging Infection Consortium
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PSI	Pandemic Sciences Institute
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
SARS	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organization

Glossary of Key Terms

Term	Definition
Affected community	A group of people with shared context who have direct or indirect experience of an outbreak. This might include those diagnosed, their close contacts, and people who identify with affected populations through shared geographical or social context, experience, or identity. ¹
Community engagement	The process of working with communities to address health-related issues, promote wellbeing, and support changes in behaviour, environments, or policies. Engagement may be community-oriented, community-based, community-managed, or community-owned. ²
Infectious disease outbreak	A sudden and unexpected rise in cases of a disease caused by a pathogen in a defined community, geographical area, or time period. ³
Outbreak response organisation	Organisations that are directly involved in preventing, investigating and/or managing outbreaks. ⁴
People with lived experience	Individuals who personally have or had the outbreak-related infectious disease of concern. This does not require having received care or treatment. ⁵
Psychosocial support	Actions that address psychological, emotional and social needs of individuals, families and communities and help people care for themselves and their relationships with others. ⁶
Risk communication	The real-time exchange of information, advice, and opinions between experts or officials and people who currently, or may in future face a hazard or threat to their physical, economic or social wellbeing. ⁷
Social listening	The process of collecting and analysing information from media, online platforms, and communities to understand public beliefs, narratives, attitudes, and concerns. ⁸
Stigma	The denial of social acceptance of a person or group based on an attribute seen as discrediting. This includes negative beliefs and attitudes (prejudice) and behaviours, including unwarranted avoidance and differential treatment, which may lead to disadvantage, harm, or exclusion (discrimination). ⁹ Stigma can manifest in interpersonal interactions (social and provider/ authority-related stigma), laws and policies (structural stigma), and self-perception (internalised or self stigma). ¹⁰

Introduction to the Guidelines

Background

Stigma is a pervasive challenge in infectious disease outbreaks. It has repeatedly been observed to deepen socioeconomic divides, hinder outbreak response efforts, and cause lasting harm to individuals and communities.¹¹

Stigma is shaped by disease- and context-specific factors such as cultural norms, policies, and systemic biases.¹² This means that the experiences and impacts of stigma are not uniform; they are shaped by intersecting aspects of identity and social position, such as gender, race, age, socioeconomic status, and disability. These intersections can compound disadvantages and must be considered when designing equitable and effective responses.

Stigma is also shaped by the actions taken to control an outbreak. If poorly implemented, control measures may act as a source of stigma and may therefore be the drivers of stigma that are most readily addressable. For example, measures such as contact tracing and risk communication can inadvertently disclose personal information or reinforce negative stereotypes.¹³ However, these risks can be mitigated through careful design.

Despite growing recognition of the harms of outbreak-related stigma, practical guidance on how to prevent or reduce it is limited.¹⁴ Responders lack clear frameworks to support stigma-sensitive decision-making, and there is limited evidence-based or expert-endorsed guidance on which interventions are likely to be most successful. These gaps can make it harder to recognise when response efforts may be contributing to stigma, or to respond quickly when stigma emerges.

Experience in established infectious disease contexts such as HIV has demonstrated how discriminatory policies can entrench and institutionalise stigma, particularly for groups already subject to marginalisation.¹² However, it has also shown that stigma can be addressed through coordinated public health action.¹⁵

While new and re-emerging infectious disease outbreaks would benefit from similar attention, they differ in important ways. Rapidly evolving information about transmission and severity often fuels fear and uncertainty. Public health measures often also involve some degree of enforced separation. Additionally, epidemiological surveillance activities must balance the privacy and autonomy of affected individuals with the broader public good. These dynamics call for approaches that are both timely and tailored to the realities of outbreak response.

A cross-outbreak approach is anticipated to improve preparedness.¹⁶ Infectious disease outbreaks are often sporadic and short-lived. Developing effective stigma tools in a timely manner is particularly difficult during the early phases of a response, when information is limited, and systems are under pressure. Yet, this period is also when the tone of public messaging and policy is shaped, and when affected individuals and marginalised groups may be particularly vulnerable to stigma.¹⁷ Preparing flexible resources in advance offers a practical path forward. This aligns with the “disease X” preparedness principle: planning for future outbreak events even before their specific characteristics are known.

These guidelines are a collaborative effort to provide outbreak response organisations with practical guidance for mitigating stigma in infectious disease outbreaks, with a focus on both avoiding harm and supporting affected communities.

Objectives

The guidelines leverage available evidence and diverse expert contributions to:

1. Establish a set of **guiding principles** for stigma reduction in the context of infectious disease outbreaks.
2. Develop **actionable recommended interventions** for organisations and personnel involved in outbreak preparedness, response, and recovery.

Target audience

These guidelines are intended for use by **outbreak response organisations**, including:

- Ministries of health and other national health agencies
- Inter-governmental organisations
- Non-governmental organisations
- Civil society and community-led organisations
- Health services
- Research teams

A note on and for the media:

Although these guidelines focus specifically on guidance for outbreak response organisations, the media also play a central role in shaping or mitigating stigma. While some components of the guidelines may not be relevant to these stakeholders, we suggest that those working in media specifically review and adopt the communication and knowledge exchange guiding principles. A range of resources for responsible reporting on infectious disease outbreaks, developed for COVID-19, are also available at:

firstdraftnews.org/long-form-article/coronavirus-resources-for-reporters/

Scope of guidance

The guidelines are designed for use **before (preparedness), during (response), and after (recovery)** infectious disease outbreaks.

They address stigmatisation of individuals or communities due to association with an outbreak-prone infectious disease.

The focus is on preventing and reducing stigma, rather than addressing its broader consequences (e.g., financial impacts).

The guidelines cover **social and provider/authority-related stigma, structural stigma, and self stigma.**

Stigma sub-domains:

Social stigma: related to social interactions with family, friends, and other members of the public

Provider/authority-related stigma: related to interactions with care providers and leaders

Structural stigma: related to unfair policies or laws within systems and institutions

Self stigma: related to internalisation of stigma and diminished self-worth

Structure and key components

These guidelines are organised into two complementary parts, reflecting the overarching logic of “first, do no harm... then, do good”. This framing recognises that effective stigma mitigation in outbreaks begins with minimising the risk of causing harm, particularly through outbreak control measures themselves, before actively implementing interventions to reduce existing stigma and support affected communities.

	Part A: Guiding principles for stigma-sensitive outbreak control	Part B: Recommended stigma reduction interventions
Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key components that should underpin all aspects of outbreak management to ensure it does not exacerbate disease-related stigma. • Grounded in human rights and ethical principles and reflect expert consensus on the high likelihood of delivering benefit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities that could be introduced to reduce outbreak-related stigma. • Grounded in best available evidence and endorsed based on expert consensus.
Supporting content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each principle is supported by a set of <i>good practice indicators</i>: observable, actionable checks that together demonstrate alignment with the principle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each recommendation includes <i>implementation notes and examples, types of stigma addressed, and a summary of the evidence and considerations</i> reviewed when determining the strength of the recommendation.
Intended use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Part A to check whether your organisation’s policies, communications, and interventions could exacerbate outbreak-related stigma. • The guiding principles are also provided in checklist format (page 49) to support practical application and re-evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Part B if you are looking to implement a specific programme, campaign, intervention, or activity to reduce outbreak-related stigma at each phase of an outbreak. • Unlike the guiding principles, it is not expected that all recommended interventions will be applicable to or possible for all actors in all contexts.

Development process

The methods for developing these guidelines were informed by the WHO handbook for guideline development.¹⁸ The methods are summarised below, with further detail provided in the relevant annexes.

Part A: ISARIC Guiding Principles for Stigma-Sensitive Outbreak Response

Overview of the guiding principles

The ISARIC guiding principles are key components that should underpin all aspects of outbreak management to avoid exacerbating stigma. They are grounded in **human rights** and **ethical principles** and reflect **expert consensus** on their high likelihood of delivering **unequivocal benefit**, though often difficult to quantify and/or synthesise.¹⁹ Each principle is supported by a set of good practice indicators. These are observable, actionable checks that together demonstrate alignment with the principle.

These guiding principles and associated practice indicators can be used to assess whether an outbreak response organisation's policies, communications, and interventions are aligned with stigma-sensitive approaches. They are also available in checklist format (**Annex 8**) to support practical application.

There are nine guiding principles grouped into **three themes**:

- i. Communication and knowledge exchange
- ii. Policy and governance
- iii. Service design and delivery

Each principle includes:

- A guiding statement
- A brief explanation of the underlying rationale
- A set of good practice indicators

i. Communication and knowledge exchange principles

Principle 1: Person-centred language

Guiding principle:

All public health communication should reflect the humanity and dignity of affected populations.

Rationale:

This principle reflects an understanding that language can shape perceptions and behaviours and contribute to empathy or stigma. The principle aligns with the right to dignity under Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR).²⁰ Respectful language is also consistent with the medical duty to uphold patient dignity as outlined in the World Medical Association Declaration of Geneva.²¹

Good practice indicators:

- Criminalising or violent metaphors are not used (e.g., people are not referred to as “suspects”, ‘war on disease’ analogies are avoided).
- Individuals are not reduced to their disease status in public communications (e.g., people are not referred to as “carriers” or “superspreaders”).
- Fear-based portrayals are not used (e.g., imagery does not only focus on the most severe or terminal stages of the illness).
- Public and internal communications about the outbreak centre the lived experience of those affected, including recovery stories.

Principle 2: Blame-free messaging

Guiding principle:

Messaging should not imply that specific groups are responsible for the outbreak.

Rationale:

Infectious disease outbreaks result from a complex combination of factors, not the actions of any specific group. Messaging that portrays disease as innately linked to a particular population can exacerbate discrimination. Avoiding blame reflects obligations under Article 20 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which prohibits advocacy of national, racial, or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence.²² It is also in keeping with the right to protection against attacks upon honour and reputation (UDHR Article 12).²⁰ Blame-free naming of diseases is directly supported by the WHO's Best Practices for Naming New Human Infectious Diseases.²³

Good practice indicators:

- Media reflects the diversity of affected populations.
- Communication explains transmission-based risk (both how the disease is and is not transmitted) rather than implying risk based on identity.
- Messaging does not imply moral failure or irresponsibility (e.g., over-stating preventability through basic hygiene).
- Disease names that reference places, animals, or groups of people are avoided and/or challenged.
- Public communications promote social cohesion and solidarity and counter misinformation that may further 'us versus them' social divisions.

Principle 3: Two-way communication

Guiding principle:

Outbreak communication mechanisms should be designed for two-way engagement with communities.

Rationale:

Effective communication that involves discussion rather than unidirectional instruction can help ensure community concerns are addressed and messaging is contextually-sensitive. This principle upholds the right to participation (ICCPR, Article 25)²² and aligns with WHO's definition of risk communication.⁷ It is also in keeping with the mandate for inclusive engagement in outbreak response (WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks),²⁴ and reflects the ethical values of respect for autonomy and informed decision-making.

Good practice indicators:

- Mechanisms exist for community feedback, questions, and knowledge sharing.
- Social listening channels are maintained and reviewed with communities.
- Public health communications are co-designed with affected groups.
- Systems are in place to adapt communication based on community feedback and emerging concerns.

ii. Policy and governance principles

Principle 4: Shared decision-making

Guiding principle:

Affected communities should be meaningfully engaged in decisions that impact them.

Rationale:

Affected communities should have a voice in the actions that influence their wellbeing. This involvement also helps to design more effective and appropriate interventions. This principle reflects Article 5 of the Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights,²⁵ which affirms that individuals and communities should be involved in decision-making processes and aligns with the right to participate in public affairs under ICCPR (Article 25).²² It highlights the importance of inclusive engagement in outbreak response (WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks)²⁴ and supports an ethical commitment to autonomy. It is also consistent with the WHO Framework on Integrated People-Centred Health Services,²⁶ which presents a vision in which all people have equal access to quality health services that are co-produced.

Good practice indicators:

- Diverse affected community members/groups are included in decision-making structures and empowered to shape outbreak response.
- The perspectives of groups facing unique risks (e.g., youth, incarcerated people) are sought and incorporated into response efforts.
- Rapid community engagement mechanisms exist for time-sensitive decisions.
- The scope and limitations of engagement processes are transparently communicated.
- Community engagement initiatives allow for low-profile or anonymous involvement.
- Community collaborators are offered financial and/or training support to enable meaningful engagement.
- Structures are in place to facilitate and support community-led interventions.

Principle 5: Intra-organisational stigma reduction

Guiding principle:

Institutions should model the inclusive and transparent behaviours they promote.

Rationale:

Institutional trustworthiness is a prerequisite for building lasting community trust. Stigma needs to be addressed within institutions before it can be effectively addressed externally. Promoting institutional transparency and fairness supports the right to non-discrimination (ICCPR, Article 26)²² and accountability in health systems (WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks).²⁴

Good practice indicators:

- Transparent, inclusive hiring practices are in place, with explicit consideration of intersecting forms of marginalisation.
- Confidential whistleblowing and discrimination reporting systems are accessible and have clear escalation pathways.
- Institutional policies and procedures are actively reviewed to identify stigma risks and adapted in response to risks identified.
- All outbreak response staff are trained in non-stigmatising care practices.
- Pay structures are transparent and equitable, with consideration for the local context and level of risk.

Principle 6: Monitoring and evaluation

Guiding principle:

The effectiveness and adverse effects of outbreak control measures and stigma reduction interventions should be assessed and transparently reported.

Rationale:

Evaluating and documenting stigma-related outcomes enables shared learning and strengthens accountability in outbreak response. Transparent reporting supports the right to benefit from scientific progress under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Article 15,²⁷ by ensuring that knowledge generated through public health interventions informs future practice. It also helps prevent repeated harms and promotes oversight, aligning with the UDHR, Article 12,²⁰ which protects against arbitrary interference with privacy and reputation. This principle is reinforced by the WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks,²⁴ which highlights the importance of recognising social harms, crediting community contributions, and transparently reporting outcomes.

Good practice indicators:

- Adverse psychosocial effects of outbreak control interventions are monitored, formally reported, and used to inform practices going forward.
- Evaluation strategies are in place for stigma reduction interventions and the outcomes are formally evaluated and documented.
- Reporting includes a clear description of the extent and nature of community engagement.
- Community members involved in research or response efforts are appropriately credited according to their preferences.

iii. Service design and delivery principles

Principle 7: Dignified, accessible services

Guiding principle:

Outbreak services should be designed to minimise dehumanisation and alienation.

Rationale:

Service environments that undermine privacy, use othering terminology, or treat affected people disrespectfully can reinforce stigma and deepen social exclusion. This principle is supported by the WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks,²⁴ which states that individuals subject to control measures should have the means to communicate with their loved ones and the outside world. Service environments that undermine privacy, use othering terminology, or treat individuals' belongings disrespectfully can reinforce stigma and deepen social exclusion. This principle also reflects the rights to dignity and equal access to public service (UDHR, Articles 1 and 21).²⁰

Good practice indicators:

- Othering imagery and terminology are avoided in labelling facilities and procedures (e.g., naming facilities "treatment centres" instead of "isolation units").
- Facilities and procedures are designed to protect privacy and avoid inadvertent disclosure (e.g., not using disease-labelled vehicles or separate healthcare facility entrances).
- Facilities and services are accessible to those facing intersecting marginalisation (including people who are displaced).
- Personal belongings are handled respectfully, only removed when necessary, and returned when possible.

Principle 8: Proportionate evidence-based measures

Guiding principle:

Outbreak measures should be evidence-based and no more restrictive than necessary to minimise social disruption.

Rationale:

Introducing excessively restrictive outbreak measures that are not rooted in evidence may cause unnecessary social division and erode public trust, predisposing to stigma. This principle is grounded in the Siracusa Principles,²⁸ which specify that limitations on rights during health emergencies must be necessary, proportionate, and the least restrictive means available to achieve a legitimate aim. It reflects the right to the highest attainable standard of health under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Article 12, and the right to benefit from scientific progress under Article 15.²⁷ The WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues in Infectious Disease Outbreaks²⁴ states that restrictions on movement and other control measures should be supported by the best available evidence, regularly reassessed, and implemented in ways that minimise social harm.

Good practice indicators:

- Interventions, guidelines, and procedures are aligned with best available evidence, including social and behavioural science.
- Transmission-based precautions, such as personal protective equipment use, reflect the latest evidence on infection risk and transmission.
- Facilities and standard operating procedures are designed and adapted to optimise safe contact between people receiving care and loved ones (e.g., facilitated digital contact, proportionate visitor restrictions).
- Financial and material losses are minimised and adequately compensated for.
- Families are given the opportunity to confirm the identity of a body prior to burial and perform safe closure practices.

Principle 9: Integrated psychosocial care

Guiding principle:

Psychosocial support should be accessible to affected populations and frontline workers as part of outbreak management.

Rationale:

Psychosocial and social well-being is a critical component of health and plays an important role in reducing the occurrence and internalisation of stigma. Providing psychosocial support is in line with the WHO Constitution's²⁹ statement that extension to all peoples of the benefits of medical, psychological and related knowledge is essential to the fullest attainment of health. The WHO Guidance on Ethical Issues

in Infectious Disease Outbreaks²⁴ states that efforts should be made to support the financial, social, and professional reintegration of individuals who have been subject to restriction of movement.

Providing support for frontline workers aligns with the WHO Framework on Integrated People-Centred Health Services,²⁶ which emphasises that carers should be supported, and operate in supportive environments and reflects the right to social protection and to just and favourable conditions of work (UDHR Article 22 and 23).²⁰

Good practice indicators:

- Outbreak planning and management includes psychosocial support for community members directly and indirectly affected by the outbreak.
- Frontline workers have access to psychosocial support.
- Funding for psychosocial support is included in response and recovery budgets.
- Support allocation takes into account non-medical impacts of the outbreak such as income loss, grief, and caregiving needs, with sensitivity to gender disparities in distribution of caregiving responsibilities.

Part B: Recommended Stigma Reduction Interventions

Overview of the stigma reduction interventions

The recommended stigma reduction interventions are **expert-endorsed activities** that could be introduced to reduce outbreak-related stigma, **based on best available evidence**. The purpose of the recommended interventions is to provide evidence-based, expert-endorsed options for organisational groups seeking to reduce stigma towards directly and/or indirectly affected populations at each phase of an outbreak. Unlike the guiding principles, it is not expected that all recommended interventions will be possible for all actors. Application of the interventions should be context-sensitive and make use of existing structures and resources as far as possible.

There is indirect evidence from HIV research showing a dose-response whereby participants exposed to multiple stigma reduction intervention approaches showed greater reductions in stigmatising attitudes than participants only exposed to one intervention.³⁰ It is therefore advised to adopt multiple interventions simultaneously where feasible.

To allow actors to think about what they could implement at each phase of the outbreak, the recommended interventions are organised into three sections, focused on stigma mitigation in:

Interventions were designated to the phase in which they were considered most relevant or effective. However, there is expected to be some overlap (i.e., interventions listed within one phase may be started or continued in the adjacent phases).

Each recommended intervention includes a symbol to indicate which **sub-domain or type of stigma** it predominantly addresses (key provided below). These sub-domains correlate with the factors of the recently developed RAPID scales for cross-outbreak stigma assessment.¹⁰ This allows actors who have used the scales to prioritise interventions that address the types of stigma found to be a particular issue in their context.

Stigma sub-domains:

Social stigma: related to social interactions with family, friends, and other members of the public

Provider/authority-related stigma: related to interactions with care providers and leaders

Structural stigma: related to unfair policies or laws within systems and institutions

Self stigma: related to internalisation of stigma and diminished self-worth

Each recommended intervention includes the strength with which the expert panel recommends implementing the intervention in outbreak contexts. The strength of each recommendation takes into account the potential benefits and harms, acceptability, and feasibility of each intervention.

Strength of recommendations key:

Strong recommendation for intervention: considered beneficial and feasible in most circumstances.

Conditional recommendation for intervention: anticipated to be beneficial and feasible in many circumstances.

Support for use in further research only: possible benefits anticipated but requires further evaluation before endorsed.

Conditional recommendation against intervention: anticipated to be harmful or impractical in many circumstances.

Strong recommendation against intervention: considered harmful or impractical in most circumstances.

Each intervention also includes the overall certainty of the evidence.

Certainty of evidence key:

Very low

Low

Moderate

High

Based on GRADE and GRADE-CERQual assessments applied to the outbreak-specific systematic review, then adjusted according to appraisal of full body of supporting evidence using CERQual criteria (methodological limitations, coherence, adequacy, relevance).

Although strong recommendations are typically based on moderate or high certainty in the evidence, the WHO guideline handbook¹⁸ and Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) working group³¹ identify five specific situations where a strong recommendation for or against the proposed intervention may be warranted despite low or very low certainty. These include: (1) life-threatening or catastrophic situations; (2) uncertain benefit but certain harm; (3) potential equivalence, with one option clearly less risky or costly; (4) high certainty in similar benefits, with one option potentially more risky or costly; and (5) potential for catastrophic harm.

The recommended interventions are accompanied by implementation notes and examples, which are intended to give additional guidance to those interested in implementing the intervention as well as a **summary of the evidence and considerations** for each intervention. A more detailed overview of the evidence and the WHO-Integrate criteria used to assess the intervention is included in **Annex 5**.

Notes on terminology:

We use the term *recommended interventions* in recognition that not all actors will have the mandate or capacity to implement every intervention listed. A *strong recommendation* in this context means that if an organisation chooses to implement an intervention, the expert panel strongly recommends the specific approach described. It does not imply a mandatory or universal requirement.

The *certainty of evidence* ratings presented in the recommended interventions summary are drawn directly from the *quality of evidence* ratings assigned in the WHO-Integrate evidence profiles (**Annex 5**). The two terms are used in different sections of the guidelines to reflect the conventions of the underlying frameworks but refer to the same appraisal of confidence in the evidence.

Section A: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak preparedness

Strongly recommended interventions

<p>A1</p>	<p>We recommend providing stigma-sensitive training to service providers who interact with affected individuals, including providers outside health settings.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: Training content may cover confidentiality, preferred terminology, the negative impacts of stigma, and cultural sensitivity. Training should be integrated into established health- or service-related curricula to optimise uptake and feasibility, particularly in resource-limited settings. The intervention is expected to have maximum benefit if delivered to all interacting with individuals seeking care or involved in quarantine, treatment, or burial. This includes pharmacists, herbalists, interpreters, faith-based care providers, veterinary staff, public health practitioners, and law enforcement officers, who are often first points of contact. Training modalities that have been effective in established infectious disease contexts include role-play, lived experience testimonies, facilitated discussions, and self-guided training and assessment (often in combination).

This intervention is strongly recommended despite limited evidence in outbreak contexts due to concerns about high risk of harm if not implemented. This is on the premise that inaction (i.e., business-as-usual) would perpetuate provider-related stigma, contributing to care-seeking hesitancy.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings on the impact of stigma-sensitive training for service providers, but moderate- to high-quality systematic reviews from established infectious disease contexts^{32–34} suggest that information provision and skills-based approaches can reduce provider-related stigma. Studies have predominantly focused on healthcare workers. One study on police officer training for mental health found that role-play with actors reduced negative behaviours and was cost-effective.³⁵

Stakeholder interviews and open-text survey responses supported the relevance of such training for a broad range of providers and highlighted its potential to improve health-related interactions. A qualitative study of Ebola response teams noted that collective pre-deployment training improved team competence.³⁶ The intervention is considered broadly acceptable, with low intrusiveness, and likely to increase health equity. Its feasibility is dependent on the availability of skilled educators, proactive leadership, and sufficient frontline worker time capacity.

<p>A2</p>	<p>We recommend including stigma awareness as a component of health education initiatives for children and adolescents, particularly when an outbreak may affect these age groups.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: This can include interactive activities (e.g., simulations) and lived experience narratives (e.g., video storytelling, books, guest speakers) and may be incorporated into school curricula. The intervention should be tailored to highest risk age categories and developed in consultation with/led by young people of the relevant age group.

This intervention is strongly endorsed by the expert panel despite limited evidence due to concerns about a high risk of harm if not implemented (business-as-usual as comparator) including loss of education for affected children.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is very low certainty empirical evidence for this intervention from a single qualitative study in an outbreak setting, which reported that school leadership encouraging support for children recovering from Ebola disease was perceived to improve reintegration.³⁷ This is supported by indirect evidence from two low- to moderate-quality systematic reviews in established infectious disease contexts, which found that child-focused stigma reduction interventions – particularly those using educational and interactional techniques such as youth-led sessions, printed comics, and video storytelling – were associated with improved peer attitudes and reduced avoidance behaviours, especially when framed as life skills education and supported by school leadership.^{38,39}

Stakeholder interviews and open-text survey responses indicated support for school-based engagement, especially when children are affected by the illness, and during reintegration after illness. Respondents described harmful responses by peers and teachers when affected children returned to school, and suggested that schools be further considered in outbreak planning. These interventions are generally considered acceptable with low intrusiveness. While development of materials and mobilisation of educators may require additional resources, integration into existing school health education programmes may enhance feasibility. Evidence of cost-effectiveness is limited, but previous interventions have been delivered at relatively low cost.^{38,39}

<h1>A3</h1>	<p>We recommend pre-designing psychosocial support interventions that can be delivered under strict infection control measures.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: Most supporting evidence is in relation to video and online services or resources. However, non-digital alternatives suggested and tested by stakeholders include radio or phone communication between psychosocial support staff and people receiving care, and training psychosocial support staff on infection prevention and control as part of outbreak preparedness to allow them to provide support under strict infection control conditions. The latter approach should include adequate budget and supervision, pre-designed training modules, and staffing plans to reduce reliance on ad hoc measures or underprepared teams. Implementation should build on pre-existing structures where possible. In resource-limited settings, interventions could include pamphlets or training other affected community members to deliver psychosocial support. The WHO Centre for Health Development provides further resources to guide integration of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services into crisis and disaster management structures during each outbreak phase.⁴⁰

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is moderate certainty evidence from two COVID-19-related randomised control trials (RCTs) that digitally administered psychosocial support resources are effective in reducing perceived social stigma and internalised/self stigma for those with the illness or a demographic/geographic association.^{41,42} This is supported by indirect evidence from established infectious disease contexts, which suggest that a wide range of psycho-educational and social empowerment approaches are effective at mitigating self stigma, including individual and group-based interventions.^{34,43,44} From available data, these interventions appear to mostly be effective in the short term (<1 month).^{41,42}

Stakeholder interviews offered support for psychosocial interventions, but highlighted the importance of preparedness, training, and supervision. Surveys across three countries indicated varying support for increased psychosocial services (75%, 63% and 41% of respondents supportive in Uganda (Ebola disease), Bangladesh (Nipah virus disease) and United Kingdom (UK) (mpox) respectively, although this may be informed by existing support services). Stigma associated with seeking psychosocial support may limit uptake in some settings and cost and feasibility is expected to vary depending on the number of people affected by the outbreak, specific technology, and human resource requirements.

Conditionally recommended interventions

<p>A4</p>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> facilitating community dialogues about relevant infectious diseases and stigma in outbreak-prone areas as part of outbreak preparedness.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	<p>Certainty of evidence: Very low</p>

Implementation notes: This may be implemented through training and funding community health teams or adding stigma as a discussion topic for existing community engagement work. Discussions can cover general topics like germ theory, personal protective equipment, vaccines, and ways to care for others without physical contact. For example, in Bangladesh, the Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee’s Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene programme trained community health workers to lead regular household visits and courtyard meetings.⁴⁵ There is an opportunity to incorporate stigma reduction, such as facilitating contact with people with lived experience of outbreaks, into these types of initiatives.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated net benefit. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and consideration: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings on the impact of community dialogues on stigma, but stakeholder interviews and survey responses suggest community-led education may help address fear and mistrust that often drive stigma. Indirect evidence from low- to moderate-quality systematic reviews in established infectious disease contexts suggests that community-based educational interventions can reduce social stigma, but caution that incomplete or poorly delivered messages may reduce effectiveness or inadvertently reinforce stigma.^{39, 46, 47} A study on Nipah virus communication in Bangladesh found that participatory, image-based communication improved public understanding and trust in prevention messages.⁴⁸

Stakeholder interviews highlighted the perceived value of pre-outbreak engagement, with community dialogues viewed as more effective than top-down messaging campaigns. Open-text survey responses were similarly supportive. The intervention is considered generally acceptable, though its intrusiveness may vary depending on implementation. Feasibility is dependent on funding, availability of trained personnel, and existing community health and engagement structures, with no direct evidence on cost-effectiveness. While the intervention may help build trust and reduce social stigma, conclusions remain limited by the lack of direct empirical evidence.

<h1>A5</h1>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> incorporating person-centred features into personal protective equipment design and protocols to minimise depersonalisation.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	

Implementation notes: Where personal protective equipment (PPE) use is necessary, simple adjustments such as attaching names or faces can help maintain a sense of personhood and emotional connection, especially in high-barrier care environments. The PPE Portrait Project, which involved Ebola outbreak responders wearing portrait photos on their protective suits, is an example that illustrates how small design changes to outbreak protocols can support more person-centred care.⁴⁹ PPE should still be used judiciously, with decisions grounded in infection risk rather than fear.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated benefit and low likelihood of harm. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings evaluating the stigma impact of incorporating human-centred design features into PPE. However, stakeholder interviews and survey responses suggest that depersonalisation associated with PPE use may contribute to stigma and reduce quality of care. Indirect evidence from a moderate-quality systematic review in established infectious disease contexts highlights the importance of effective patient-provider communication in facilitating health interventions and reducing barriers to care.³²

Stakeholders described the use of names on PPE and avoiding over-use of PPE as a feasible and low-cost way to support more human interactions in high-barrier environments. Acceptability was high amongst stakeholders, and the intervention is considered minimally intrusive. Community survey responses highlighted the importance of enabling physical caregiving through adequate protective equipment. Feasibility may vary depending on design elements and supply chain factors, but simple adaptations are likely to be implementable in most settings. Although cost-effectiveness analyses have not been published, minimal-resource adaptations are likely to be inexpensive.

<p>A6</p>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> collaborating on preparedness activities with community members affected by previous outbreaks or illnesses with transferable learnings.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	<p>Certainty of evidence: Very low</p>

Implementation notes: This may include working together through strategy and communication development meetings, simulation exercises, and policy consultations. For example, people living with HIV often have insights that are transferable to other conditions such as mpox. People affected by one outbreak are also often interested in helping to prepare for subsequent outbreaks of the same disease. For instance, in preparing for future Zika outbreaks, it may be helpful to engage women’s health and disability rights groups that were involved in the response during the epidemic in Brazil.⁵⁰ It is important to provide sufficient resources and training to community volunteers to facilitate involvement. Included community members should represent a diversity of lived experiences, and include individuals with marginalised identities.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated net benefit. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings on this intervention, but stakeholder interviews described benefits such as enhanced trust, more relevant interventions, and institutional memory. Indirect evidence from a moderate-quality systematic review in the context of HIV noted that while trained community members found involvement in response coordination challenging, they also found the experience rewarding.³⁹ An additional methodologically sound qualitative study from a previous Ebola outbreak highlighted barriers to effective engagement, including, poor communication, under-compensation, and inadequate institutional support.⁵¹

Stakeholders described the involvement of affected communities in preparedness activities as valuable for drawing on past experiences and avoiding repeated mistakes. Acceptability was considered high, though potential harms include overburdening participants and increased identifiability. Feasibility depends on adequate human resourcing, funding, and support structures to avoid reliance on goodwill. Integration may be enhanced through partnerships with community-led organisations. The intervention may support health equity and improve the relevance of outbreak preparedness strategies, but conclusions are limited by the very low certainty and indirect nature of available evidence.

Section B: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak response

Strongly recommended interventions

<p>B1</p>	<p>We <u>recommend</u> embedding stigma reduction messages in public health education and risk communication efforts.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: Information provision is often suggested and widely used to address stigma, but evidence indicates that improving knowledge about an outbreak does not necessarily reduce stigma unless combined with stigma-specific messaging. Stigma reduction messages can be included in daily briefings, posters, and social media, or can be disseminated through partnership with local leaders and representatives. Content can foster a sense of solidarity or collectivism, emphasise reciprocity (e.g., “treat others as you would like to be treated”), and suggest ways to safely support affected individuals. Consistency across formats is helpful for reinforcing key messages. These key messages should be shared with the media.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is moderate certainty evidence from two COVID-19 RCTs that embedding stigma reduction messages into public health campaigns can reduce fear and stigmatising attitudes compared to no intervention or general health information alone.^{52, 53} Low certainty qualitative evidence describes targeted community-led efforts by religious leaders and community elders to support the reintegration of people recovered from Ebola disease.^{37, 54} Indirect systematic reviews support the use of public education and mass media to reduce stigma but in many cases did not specify if this education is about the disease, associated stigma, or both.^{33, 34, 39, 43, 46, 55} The reviews note that messaging is more effective when consistent and developed with attention to local beliefs.

Non-interventional studies found that contradictory messaging contributed to confusion and stigma, and suggested that visual formats might improve communication.⁵⁶ Drawing on experiences of the 2003 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) outbreak, a qualitative study recommended that messages be delivered through trusted local channels to supplement broader media campaigns.⁵⁷ Stakeholders interviewed noted that factual information alone is often insufficient and, in some cases, may worsen stigma. Interviewees highlighted the value of involving trusted, locally embedded messengers and incorporating empathetic messaging. Public education and stigma reduction messaging were the most supported stigma reduction interventions across the three survey contexts.

<h1>B2</h1>	<p>We <u>recommend</u> facilitating public engagement with affected individuals' experiences.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: Improved public understanding of how people are affected by the outbreak and associated stigma can be facilitated through digital technology, arts-based approaches, or public testimonies. A particularly promising method is participatory video, in which affected individuals are taught how to create short documentaries or films about their own experiences, which are then shared publicly. Other possible formats include poetry, theatre, newspaper, or community radio. These interventions are considered helpful for fostering empathy and humanising the outbreak. Evidence suggests that 'social contact' focused interventions (i.e., interacting with people from the stigmatised group) are most effective under conditions of equal status among participants, cooperative interaction, institutional support, real-world engagement and when they counter assumptions or stereotypes.⁵⁸ These interventions may involve individuals with the illness, those who have recovered, or their family members, and remain relevant during the recovery phase. Explicit safeguards – including informed consent, clear opt-out mechanisms, and privacy protections – are needed to mitigate risks of re-traumatisation or social repercussions. Interventions should make use of pre-existing engagement and communication channels when possible.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is low certainty evidence from one RCT showing that a brief video portraying a person with COVID-19 discussing their experiences reduced public stigma.⁵³ Very low certainty evidence from a qualitative study on Ebola disease found that survivor-led peer education improved reintegration and reduced stigma more effectively than top-down campaigns.³⁷ Indirect evidence from moderate- to high-quality systematic reviews in established disease contexts supports participatory video, testimonials, and arts-based formats as effective approaches to foster empathy, shift attitudes, and reduce stigma at community and individual levels.^{33, 34, 39, 44, 59}

Stakeholder interviews highlighted the role of storytelling and representation in empowering affected individuals. Survey responses showed consistent public support for hearing directly from survivors, with some respondents suggesting this approach was more effective than health worker messaging. While generally feasible and low-cost, interventions require appropriate planning, participant safeguards, and compensation. Feasibility may vary depending on format and setting.

<p>B3</p>	<p>We recommend offering accessible psychosocial support and resources to those affected by the outbreak, such as remote services during isolation.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Strongly in favour</p>	

Implementation notes: Support should extend to frontline workers, carers, household members, and others at risk of stigma (due to their work, identity, or proximity) to mitigate self/internalised stigma. This intervention is likely most effective when implemented early and repeated, since the available research suggests a short-term (<28 day) effect. While most of the available evidence is in relation to online resources, the intervention's chosen modality should be culturally aligned and make use of pre-existing structures as far as possible. The intervention may be delivered by mental health professionals (e.g. psychiatrists, psychologists), community members with specific training (e.g. lay counsellors, peer support), or be an online or printed resource. Resources may include content on managing emotional distress or the perceptions of others. The support/resources should be accessible discretely so as to avoid additional stigma often associated with seeking psychosocial support. Effort should be made to ensure the service is accessible to marginalised groups. The WHO Centre for Health Development provides further resources to guide integration of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services into crisis and disaster management structures during each outbreak phase.⁴⁰

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is moderate certainty evidence from two RCTs showing that brief, digitally delivered psychosocial interventions can reduce perceived outbreak-related stigma in the short term.^{41,42} These included an online programme for those recovering from COVID-19 and a writing-based intervention that reduced perceived COVID-19 discrimination among individuals returning from a high-risk area. Indirect evidence from moderate- to high-quality systematic reviews in established infectious disease contexts supports a range of psychosocial approaches, including peer-led counselling, lay provider interventions, and group-based formats, for reducing self stigma and related outcomes.^{33, 34, 39, 44, 59}

Stakeholder interviews indicated high acceptability, especially when support is delivered early, confidentially, and tailored to the affected group. Community support across three contexts varied substantially but may be due to differing existing support mechanisms across settings. In some contexts, accessing psychosocial services may itself be stigmatised, which could limit uptake. Feasibility is likely to vary depending on access to trained personnel and available technology, but digital platforms may improve scalability.

B4

We **recommend** co-designing, adapting and implementing stigma awareness initiatives for the local context with affected community members, including people with lived experience of the illness.

Strength of recommendation:
Strongly in favour

Certainty of evidence:
Moderate

Implementation notes: This includes mass media campaigns. There is a risk of co-design being rushed, tokenistic, and reliant on goodwill. For it to be meaningful, community engagement must be funded, provide necessary training and logistical support, allow time for genuine input, and include diverse contributors, not just those who are most visible or familiar. When possible, and of interest to affected community members, these interventions should also be led by people with lived experience. Participation should be voluntary and include discussion of potential risks, especially in relation to visibility and identifiability.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is moderate certainty evidence from two qualitative studies suggesting that co-designed public health messaging led by affected community members can reduce outbreak-related stigma.^{37,60} In the UK mpox response, community organisations helped design messaging using local colloquialisms and humour to improve reach in the context of post-COVID-19 public health fatigue.⁶⁰ In Sierra Leone, local development of stigma reduction efforts with community leaders and Ebola survivors was found to be effective in facilitating reintegration.³⁷

Indirect evidence from moderate- to high-quality systematic reviews supports participatory approaches, emphasising the importance of tailoring messaging to local beliefs and practices, building on community-proposed strategies, and ensuring accessibility to marginalised groups.^{34,44,46} Non-interventional studies supported co-designed approaches, though challenges were noted – including rushed timelines, lack of funding, and reliance on unpaid or overstretched community members.^{51,57,61} Stakeholder interviews emphasised the need for trusted messengers, community-led framing, and adaptation to different levels of health literacy. Community surveys indicated high cross-contextual support for more thoughtful messaging and demonstrated a readiness to provide input. While feasibility is generally high with sufficient planning, sustainability requires coordination, resources, and time allocation for meaningful inclusion. Ensuring messages reach communities more effectively could save communication-related costs.

Conditionally recommended interventions

<p>B5</p>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> facilitating peer support opportunities led by people with lived experience.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	

Implementation notes: Peer-led support may help reduce feelings of social isolation during recovery. Training and sustained support structures are important to ensure peer mentors are equipped and not overburdened. Participation in peer led psychosocial interventions should be voluntary and informed by local and cultural norms related to care and support. These may be embedded within the clinical setting.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated net benefit. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak contexts on the impact of peer-led support opportunities. Indirect evidence from moderate-quality systematic reviews in established infectious disease settings suggests that peer-led interventions may help improve self-esteem and facilitate social reintegration.^{39,44} These effects were linked to reduced self/internalised and anticipated stigma.^{39,44} Reviews highlighted the importance of adequate training and supervision to ensure peer mentors are well-prepared and not overburdened.^{39,44}

Stakeholder interviews offered strong endorsement of peer-led support, particularly when grounded in shared experience and delivered in trusted spaces such as community settings. Examples included survivor associations continuing to provide outreach and education post-outbreak, and peer support embedded in healthcare encounters. Acceptability is considered high when opportunities are voluntary and culturally aligned. Feasibility may depend on training, supervision, and integration with formal systems, but indirect evidence supports sustainability if well embedded.

<h1>B6</h1>	<p>We <u>suggest against</u> introducing community protection bylaws that impose fines for stigmatisation of affected persons.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditionally against</p>	

Implementation notes: Bylaws or penalties have been introduced in some outbreak contexts to deter stigmatising behaviours towards recovered individuals. Concerns include erosion of trust, social consequences for families, and reinforcement of stigma, particularly if law enforcement is involved. This approach has raised concerns about the use of coercion rather than addressing underlying drivers of stigma, such as fear, misinformation, or mistrust of authorities.

Instead, non-punitive structural changes and community support should be prioritised. Non-police actors such as village health teams or trained community representatives may be better positioned to respond to community resistance. These community protection efforts should be community-initiated, rights-respecting, proportionate and supported by education and dialogue.

This recommendation does not apply to instances of discrimination that are already prohibited under existing human rights and legal frameworks.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is very low certainty evidence from a qualitative study in Sierra Leone suggesting that community-developed protection bylaws may help reduce Ebola stigma when locally led and integrated into broader efforts.⁵⁴ However, in interviews stakeholders raised concerns about punitive approaches, especially when implemented by police or imposed without local consultation. While community members may respond positively to fair and educational enforcement, punitive or culturally inappropriate approaches risk backlash and long-term harm.

Findings from systematic reviews of established infectious diseases highlight similar tensions.^{34, 39, 59} Legal protections may support justice in some contexts, but punitive or coercive approaches may worsen stigma, particularly where trust in authorities is low. Public support for legal fines or sanctions was low across all survey settings, reinforcing the need for caution.

Support for research only

<p>B7</p>	<p>We <u>support further research</u> on the stigma-related impacts, feasibility, and acceptability of community-based quarantine, isolation, and care.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Research only</p>	

Implementation notes: Community-based quarantine, isolation, and care may be considered more acceptable, and less stigmatising, than distant institutional services, especially in contexts where institutional mistrust is a prominent concern. However, these approaches require adequate community preparation, including suitable physical and social conditions. Appropriateness may also vary substantially depending on the pathogen.

This intervention may involve facility-based care within the community or home-based care, with both requiring further assessment. Considerations need to be made for safety risks, increased household stigma, feasibility for people without traditional homes, and the burden placed on households in the case of home-based care, particularly in low-resource or overcrowded settings.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from the outbreak-related systematic review on community-based quarantine or care. A study in the context of Ebola disease in the Democratic Republic of the Congo suggests community-based quarantine for close contacts may be non-inferior for disease control but the impact on stigma was not evaluated.⁶² Stakeholder interviews highlighted both potential benefits and risks. In some settings, institutional quarantine was associated with fear, mistrust, and avoidance behaviours, including escape attempts. By contrast, community or home-based approaches were described as more acceptable, fostering dignity and trust, particularly when individuals and families were supported to monitor for symptoms.

In contrast, some interviewees expressed concern that, without sufficient preparation or support, home-based quarantine could increase psychosocial stress, place vulnerable family members at risk, or result in delayed care-seeking and ineffective infection control. Practical constraints, such as overcrowding, lack of sanitation, and subsistence living conditions, were flagged as major barriers. No affected community survey responses addressed this intervention. Overall, home-based quarantine may be less stigmatising but further research into the necessary preconditions is warranted.

Section C: Recommended interventions to mitigate stigma during outbreak recovery

Conditionally recommended interventions

<p>C1</p>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> implementing initiatives that help people who have recovered reintegrate into their households, workplaces, schools, religious practices, and other community activities.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	

Implementation notes: Includes sharing clear information on recovery timelines and guidance on safe return to work, school, and other social settings. This information should be made publicly available and provided directly to recovered individuals in a format that is easy to share with others (e.g., printed leaflets, text messages, or a website link for employers or schools) and to contexts such as schools and workplaces where appropriate. Initiatives may also include support and focused education efforts from psychosocial support staff where relevant.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated net benefit. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and considerations: Although no direct empirical evidence was identified from outbreak contexts, qualitative and indirect evidence indicates that reintegration initiatives can mitigate stigma. A systematic review found workplace anti-stigma interventions consistently improved employees' supportive behaviours in other disease contexts.³⁴ Another review highlighted the social and economic vulnerability of individuals facing stigma, including lost income and exclusion from services.³²

Stakeholder interviews described the role of psychosocial teams in reassuring families and communities, the use of recovery leaflets and web pages to support re-entry into work or school, and direct engagement with employers to encourage acceptance of recovered individuals. These actions were reported to promote community reintegration. While such initiatives are generally considered acceptable, feasibility depends on intersectoral coordination and the development of accessible, context-appropriate materials. The net economic implications are expected to favour the intervention, given that preventing recovered individuals from returning to work or education results in substantial financial losses. It is considered minimally to moderately intrusive depending on mode of delivery.

<p>C2</p>	<p>We suggest including assessment of psychosocial wellbeing as part of follow-up care for people who have recovered and offering referral to longer-term support services.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	<p>Certainty of evidence: Very low</p>

Implementation notes: Psychological and social harms often persist well beyond clinical recovery. Recovered individuals have reported feelings of isolation, distress, and suicidal ideation related to ongoing stigma, loss of livelihood, and lack of community acceptance. Follow-up services should include routine screening for psychosocial needs and clear referral pathways, to ongoing support. This is particularly important in contexts where reintegration is noted to be difficult due to stigma. Physical causes for distress or psychological disturbances should be excluded first and the implications of referral should be carefully considered. Follow-up services should be integrated into routine care as far as possible to avoid further othering and discrimination.

This intervention is conditionally supported due to limited evidence but anticipated net benefit. Further evaluation in outbreak contexts is needed.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings related to psychosocial wellbeing, but stakeholder interviews emphasised the need for follow-up care that includes assessment of psychological and social wellbeing. Stakeholders described the psychological toll of ongoing stigma following recovery, including cases of suicidal ideation, financial hardship, and persistent social exclusion. Several stakeholders highlighted the importance of routine psychosocial screening and referral as a way to identify and address stigma-related distress, drawing on models from HIV care where such systems are more commonly integrated into long-term care.

Survey responses showed mixed support for more psychosocial support across settings (75% in Uganda, 63% in Bangladesh, 41% in the UK), although this is likely informed by the current available support. The intervention is likely to be acceptable if services are voluntary and confidential. Feasibility will depend on the availability of trained personnel and existing service infrastructure, though referral points will often already exist. The implementation suggestion to integrate follow up services into routine care is supported by an ethnographic study in Hong Kong in which SARS survivors reported that separate entrances reconstructed stigma against them and made them feel as if they were still infectious, and that attending psychiatric clinics to receive support labelled them with an additional form of stigma.⁶³

<p>C3</p>	<p>We <u>suggest</u> documenting, robustly evaluating, and publishing stigma reduction efforts.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Conditional support</p>	

Implementation notes: Stigma reduction interventions are rarely evaluated during outbreaks, limiting opportunities for shared learning. Evaluation should be planned in advance and embedded into response activities. Mixed methods implementation studies are needed to assess outcomes such as feasibility, acceptability, and fidelity. Designs such as stepped wedge cluster trials can support evaluation of phased, real-time interventions. It is often helpful to have pre-prepared and or pre-approved protocols for assessing stigma reduction in outbreak responses as ethical review processes can be slow and protocols for testing biomedical interventions may take priority during an outbreak, limiting the ability to evaluate stigma reduction interventions. Results should ideally be made publicly available and free to access. Evaluation reports should include adequate details about the context, intervention, and evaluation tools or methods used.

Summary of evidence and considerations: The limited direct empirical evidence from outbreak settings evaluating stigma reduction interventions throughout the guidelines highlights this gap. Multiple systematic reviews emphasise that the lack of evaluation limits opportunities to identify effective approaches and improve future responses.^{34, 39, 43, 47, 59, 64} These reviews have noted shared challenges across infectious disease contexts such as unvalidated outcome measures, inconsistent study designs, limited assessment of long-term impact, and a lack of research from low- and middle-income settings.

One non-interventional study highlighted the failure of existing monitoring systems to capture real-time stigma patterns, particularly at the intersection of race and health.⁶⁵ Stakeholders interviewed stressed the importance of embedding evaluation into outbreak responses to understand stigma persistence and improve intervention design. While no harms were identified, acceptability depends on transparent, voluntary data collection and protection of confidentiality. Evaluation is likely to improve equity and efficiency by informing scalable, evidence-based approaches. Feasibility depends on research capacity and resourcing but can be enhanced through integration into response.

Support for research only

<p>C4</p>	<p>We support further research on the effectiveness, acceptability, and potential harms of facilitating visible contact between response workers and recovered persons.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Research only</p>	

Implementation notes: Small, symbolic gestures from trusted figures (e.g., local representatives, leaders or healthcare workers) – such as sitting together, shaking hands, or walking side by side with recovered individuals – is anecdotally reported to help address fears, contribute to community confidence in a person’s recovery, and support reintegration. However, there are also potential risks including gender and cultural sensitivities around physical contact and concerns about unwanted attention and discomfort. Further research is required to robustly explore the benefits and risks of this intervention. Alternative formats may include, healthcare workers entering recovery areas or former treatment facilities without PPE to indicate safety. When implemented, physical interactions should always be voluntary and carried out with the individual’s consent. Their impact is expected to be greatest when combined with broader community engagement.

Summary of evidence and considerations: There is no direct empirical evidence from the outbreak-related systematic review. Stakeholder interviews from Ebola disease context suggest that visible, voluntary gestures by trusted figures, such as shaking hands or sitting beside a recovered person, can help reduce fear, demonstrate safety, and support social reintegration. These actions were described as meaningful symbols of acceptance that influenced community perceptions.

The intervention is generally low cost and can be integrated into existing communication or psychosocial support activities. Acceptability appears high when gestures are consensual and culturally appropriate. However, risks include unwanted attention, discomfort, or breaches of privacy, particularly if actions are not prediscussed with the individual. Anecdotes are focused on Ebola disease, and broader applicability remains uncertain.

<p>C5</p>	<p>We support further research on the effectiveness, acceptability, and potential harms of recovery celebrations.</p>
<p>Strength of recommendation: Research only</p>	

Implementation notes: Symbolic or celebratory practices such as homecoming events or survivor walls have been used to support social reintegration following outbreaks, although no formal evaluations of these practices were identified. These practices may help shift the public focus from loss to recovery. However, safeguards would need to be in place to ensure participation is voluntary, and decisions about format and timing should rest with the recovered individual. Planning must consider the risk of unwanted visibility, potential pressure to participate, and sensitivity to those who have experienced loss. Celebration and mourning may coexist in affected communities, and public events must reflect this complexity. These interventions should ideally be led by affected community members and people with lived experience. These celebrations may also include celebrating healthcare workers. To date these interventions tend to be informally documented and the effectiveness and harms have not been robustly evaluated. Further research is needed to evaluate how effective recovery celebrations are in reducing stigma as well as their feasibility, acceptability, and applicability in different contexts.

Summary of evidence and considerations: Stakeholder interviews described examples of recovery celebrations, such as homecoming events, survivor walls, and community songs used in Ebola disease and COVID-19 responses to mark recovery and support reintegration. These practices were reported to have a positive psychological and social impact and may contribute to reducing stigma through public affirmation of safety and belonging. A national Ebola survivor celebration day was suggested in the responses to the community survey in Uganda. These accounts suggest that, in some contexts, celebration may help foster community support and counter fear-based exclusion.

However, the potential risks include unwanted visibility, pressure to participate, or emotional discomfort. Celebrations may be inappropriate or distressing for individuals who prefer a lower-profile return or in communities experiencing active grief. Acceptability is likely to depend heavily on individual preference, timing, and cultural context. No evidence of cost or effectiveness is available beyond anecdotal accounts.

Interventions discussed by the expert panel but not included in the final guidelines (no recommendation)

Implementing recovery certificates

Reasons for no recommendation:

- Very low certainty evidence available (both in support and against).
- Concern that blanket cross-outbreak recommendation is not appropriate as may be valuable in some contexts but may also have the capacity to be stigma-inducing or be used as an instrument of bureaucratic exclusion.

Implementing population-wide outbreak control measures to avoid targeted restrictions

Reasons for no recommendation:

- Very low certainty evidence available (both in support and against).
- Considered too outbreak- and context-specific.
- Concern that may be interpreted as recommending against all universal precautions.
- Concerns that, if adopted, stigma shifts to those unable to comply with the measures, e.g., due to disability, environment, or cost.
- Concern that intervention may be interpreted as endorsement of evidence-free application of interventions where they cause no benefit and result in unnecessary costs.

Introducing low-cost reassurance measures such as temperature screening

Reasons for no recommendation:

- Very low certainty evidence available (both in support and against).
- Concerns that such approaches may be appropriate in specific circumstances while, in others, they may undermine the value of evidence-based interventions.
- Concerns about low evidence of effectiveness of temperature screening for many diseases.

Providing material resources or financial support to infected or individuals recovering or to the families of the deceased

Reasons for no recommendation:

- Very low certainty evidence available (both in support and against)
- Insufficient evidence or rationale for stigma reduction, and concern about potential for furthering community divisions.
- Considered more appropriate for outbreak-specific discussion rather than cross-outbreak recommendations.

Concluding Remarks

Stigma is a recurrent and damaging feature across infectious disease outbreaks. While its drivers are complex and shaped by context, it can be mitigated through intentional, well-informed public health action. Designing responses that are sensitive to stigma is not only a matter of minimising personal harm, it can also improve public trust, support equitable access to services, and enhance the overall effectiveness of outbreak control efforts.

These guidelines bring together guiding principles and recommended interventions to support more stigma-aware decision-making across all phases of an outbreak. They draw on available evidence, expert input, and insights from affected communities. However, the evidence base remains limited, particularly in relation to implementation and impact in outbreak-specific contexts. Continued documentation and evaluation are critical to strengthen the field and avoid repeating mistakes of the past.

Reducing stigma in outbreaks requires early planning, institutional commitment, and meaningful collaboration with those most affected. The intention of these guidelines is not to offer fixed solutions, but to provide practical starting points for reflection, adaptation, and action.

Guideline Contributors

Name	Affiliation
Writing group	
Amy Paterson	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Chambrez-Zita Zauchenberger	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Mary Gouws	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Ruan Spies	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Project leadership	
Amanda Rojek	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Ashleigh Cheyne	Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Piero Olliaro	ISARIC Global Support Centre, Centre for Tropical Medicine and Global Health, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Nina Gobat	Nuffield Department of Primary Care, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Expert panel	
Anne Stangl	Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, United States
Antons Mozalevskis	World Health Organization, Headquarters, Global HIV, Hepatitis and STI Programmes, Switzerland
Eka Airlangga	Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara; Paediatric Pandemic and Outbreak Plans of Indonesia, Indonesia
Hager Saeed	The American University in Cairo, Egypt
Harun Tulunay	Positively UK; Plushealth and Sexpression; UK-CAB; NHS England HIV CRG Board, United Kingdom
Ismat Jahan Bhuiyan	Ministry of Health And Family Welfare, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Bangladesh
Jeni Stolow	Tulane University School of Public Health and Tropical Medicine, United States
Jennifer Collins	University of the West of Scotland United Kingdom

John Robert Carabeo Medina	University of the Philippines Manila; National Institutes of Health, Philippines
Kkunsu Hadson Dimitrios	Medical and Molecular Laboratories, Uganda
Laura De Almeida	National Institute for Communicable Diseases, South Africa
Maria Bertoglia	Center for Research on Pandemic Resilience, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile
Markita Suttle	Nationwide Children's Hospital, BACON Research Network, United States
Md Saiful Islam	University of New South Wales, Australia
Mumtaz Ali Khan	National Institute of Health Islamabad, Pakistan
Naveed Ahmed	University of Tabuk, Saudi Arabia
Nicole Martin	Caribbean Evaluators International; Ministry of Health and Wellness Jamaica; University of the West Indies Jamaica
Parth Sharma	Global Mental Health Peer Network (Asia/Oceania), India
Petra Gronholm	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, United Kingdom
Rayner Kay Jin Tan	Saw Swee Hock School of Public Health, National University of Singapore, Singapore
Rihab Yazidi	Pasteur Institute of Tunis, Tunisia
Samuel Tomczyk	University of Greifswald; German Center for Child and Adolescent Health (DZKJ), partner site Greifswald/Rostock, Germany
Shreyus Sukhija	Global Mental Health Peer Network (Asia/Oceania), India
Toru Takenaga	Japan Institute for Health Security; National Institute of Infectious Diseases; Department of Diagnostic Testing and Technology Research, Japan
Ursin Bayisenge	University of Global Health Equity, Rwanda
Zeb Jamrozik	University of Melbourne, Australia, and University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Additional data collection leads (stakeholder interviews and surveys)	
Olive Kabajaasi	WALIMU, Uganda
Nathan Kenya-Mugisha	WALIMU, Uganda
Tonmoy Sarkar	icddr,b, Bangladesh
Syed Satter	icddr,b, Bangladesh
Graphic design	
Beatrice Bosch	Anton Bosch Consulting and Design, South Africa

Funding

The development of these guidelines was funded by a University of Oxford Medical Sciences' Division Improving Equitable Access to Healthcare grant and supported by the Wellcome Trust [303666/Z/23/Z]; UK International Development [301542-403]; and the Gates Foundation [INV-063472].

ISARIC Anti-stigma Guiding Principles and Good Practice Indicators Checklist

Communication and knowledge exchange

Guiding principles	Good practice indicators (In practice, this means...)
1. All health communication should reflect the humanity and dignity of affected populations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Criminalising or violent metaphors are not used (e.g., people are not referred to as “suspects”, war on disease analogies are avoided).<input type="checkbox"/> Individuals are not reduced to their disease status in public communications (e.g., people are not referred to as “carriers” or “superspreaders”).<input type="checkbox"/> Fear-based portrayals are not used (e.g., imagery only focusing on the most severe or terminal stages of the illness).<input type="checkbox"/> Public and internal communications about the outbreak centre the lived experience of those affected, including recovery stories.
2. Messaging should not imply that specific groups are responsible for the outbreak.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Media reflects the diversity of affected populations.<input type="checkbox"/> Communication explains transmission-based risk (both how the disease is and is not transmitted) rather than implying risk based on identity.<input type="checkbox"/> Messaging does not imply moral failure or irresponsibility (e.g., overstating preventability through basic hygiene).<input type="checkbox"/> Disease names that reference places, animals, or groups of people are avoided and/or challenged.<input type="checkbox"/> Public communications promote social cohesion and solidarity and counter misinformation that may further ‘us versus them’ social divisions.
3. Outbreak communication mechanisms should be designed for two-way engagement with communities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Mechanisms exist for community feedback, questions, and knowledge sharing.<input type="checkbox"/> Social listening channels are maintained and reviewed with communities.<input type="checkbox"/> Public health communications are co-designed with affected groups<input type="checkbox"/> Systems are in place to adapt communication based on community feedback and emerging concerns.

Policy and governance

Guiding principles	Good practice indicators (In practice, this means...)
4. Affected communities should be meaningfully engaged in decisions that impact them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Diverse affected community members/groups are included in decision-making structures and empowered to shape outbreak response.<input type="checkbox"/> The perspectives of groups facing unique risks (e.g. youth, incarcerated people) are sought and incorporated into response efforts.<input type="checkbox"/> Rapid community engagement mechanisms exist for time-sensitive decisions.<input type="checkbox"/> The scope and limitations of engagement processes are transparently communicated.<input type="checkbox"/> Community engagement initiatives allow for low-profile or anonymous involvement.<input type="checkbox"/> Community collaborators are offered financial and/or training support to enable meaningful engagement.<input type="checkbox"/> Structures are in place to facilitate and support community-led interventions.
5. Outbreak response institutions should model the inclusive and transparent behaviours they promote.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Transparent, inclusive hiring practices are in place, with explicit consideration of intersecting forms of marginalisation.<input type="checkbox"/> Confidential whistleblowing and discrimination reporting systems are accessible and have clear escalation pathways.<input type="checkbox"/> Institutional policies and procedures are actively reviewed to identify stigma risks and adapted in response to risks identified.<input type="checkbox"/> All outbreak response staff are trained in non-stigmatising care practices.<input type="checkbox"/> Pay structures are transparent and equitable, with consideration for the local context and level of risk.
6. The effectiveness and adverse effects of outbreak control measures and stigma reduction interventions should be assessed and transparently reported.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Adverse psychosocial effects of outbreak control interventions are monitored, formally reported, and used to inform practices going forward.<input type="checkbox"/> Evaluation strategies are in place for stigma reduction interventions and the outcomes are formally evaluated and documented.<input type="checkbox"/> Reporting includes a clear description of the extent and nature of community engagement.<input type="checkbox"/> Community members involved in research or response efforts are appropriately credited according to their preferences.

Service design and delivery

Guiding principles	Good practice indicators (In practice, this means...)
<p>7. Outbreak services should be designed to minimise dehumanisation and alienation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Othering imagery and terminology are avoided in labelling facilities and procedures (e.g., naming facilities “treatment centres” instead of “isolation units”). <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities and procedures are designed to protect privacy and avoid inadvertent disclosure (e.g., not using disease-labelled vehicles or separate healthcare facility entrances). <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities and services are accessible to those facing intersecting marginalisation (including people who are displaced). <input type="checkbox"/> Personal belongings are handled respectfully, only removed when necessary, and returned when possible.
<p>8. Outbreak measures are evidence-based and no more restrictive than necessary to minimise social disruption.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Interventions, guidelines, and procedures are aligned with best available evidence, including social and behavioural science. <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission-based precautions, such as personal protective equipment use, reflect the latest evidence on infection risk and transmission. <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities and standard operating procedures are designed and adapted to optimise safe contact between people receiving care and loved ones (e.g., facilitated digital contact, proportionate visitor restrictions). <input type="checkbox"/> Interventions such as isolation and treatment take place within communities as far as possible. <input type="checkbox"/> Financial and material losses are minimised and adequately compensated for. <input type="checkbox"/> Families are given the opportunity to confirm the identity of a body prior to burial and perform safe closure practices.
<p>9. Psychosocial support should be accessible to affected populations and frontline workers as part of outbreak management.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Outbreak planning and management includes psychosocial support for community members directly and indirectly affected by the outbreak. <input type="checkbox"/> Frontline workers have access to psychosocial support. <input type="checkbox"/> Funding for psychosocial support is included in response and recovery budgets. <input type="checkbox"/> Support allocation takes into account non-medical impacts of the outbreak such as income loss, grief, and caregiving needs, with sensitivity to gender disparities in distribution of caregiving responsibilities.

References

1. World Health Organization. Community-centred approaches to health emergencies: Progress, gaps and research priorities. [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/blue-print/who-covid-19-social-science-in-outbreak-report_15.08.21.pdf
2. World Health Organization. Community engagement: a health promotion guide for universal health coverage in the hands of the people [Internet]. 2020. [cited 2025 July 23] Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240010529>
3. World Health Organization Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Disease outbreaks | Health topics [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23] Available from: <http://www.emro.who.int/health-topics/disease-outbreaks/index.html>
4. World Health Organization. Outbreak toolkit [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/outbreak-toolkit>
5. World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe. Mosaic toolkit to end stigma and discrimination in mental health [Internet]. 2024. [cited 2025 July 23] Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/379124/9789289061384-eng.pdf?sequence=2>
6. British Red Cross. Psychosocial support [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.redcross.org.uk/about-us/what-we-do/psychosocial-support>
7. World Health Organization. Risk communications [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/risk-communications>
8. World Health Organization. Social listening in infodemic management for public health emergencies: guidance on ethical considerations [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240108202>
9. Corrigan P. The stigma of disease and disability: Understanding causes and overcoming injustices. Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association; 2014
10. Paterson A, Mughogho KK, Cheyne A, Kabajaasi O, Sarkar T, Dimitrios KH, et al. The (Re)-emerging And ePIdemic Infectious Diseases (RAPID) Stigma Scales: a cross-outbreak scale development and psychometric validation study. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2025;25(11);e635-644
11. Saeed F, Mihan R, Mousavi SZ, Reniers RL, Bateni FS, Alikhani R, et al. A narrative review of stigma related to infectious disease outbreaks: what can be learned in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic? *Front Psychiatry*. 2020;11:565919
12. Stangl AL, Earnshaw VA, Logie CH, van Brakel W, Simbayi LC, Barré I, et al. The Health Stigma and Discrimination Framework: a global, crosscutting framework to inform research, intervention development, and policy on health-related stigmas. *BMC Med*. 2019;17(1):31

13. Paterson A, Jones B, Kabajaasi O, Cheyne A, Tulunay H, Hadson K, et al. An hourglass model for conceptualising stigma in infectious disease outbreaks. *Sci Rep.* 2025;15(1):15339
14. Brewis A, Wutich A. Why we should never do it: stigma as a behaviour change tool in global health. *BMJ Glob Health.* 2019;4:e001911
15. UNAIDS. The global partnership for action to eliminate all forms of HIV-related stigma and discrimination [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 23]
Available from: <https://www.unaids.org/en/topic/global-partnership-discrimination>
16. Paterson A, Olliaro PL, Rojek A. Addressing stigma in infectious disease outbreaks: a crucial step in pandemic preparedness. *Front Public Health.* 2023;11:1303679
17. Trinh DH, McKinn S, Nguyen AT, Fox GJ, Nguyen AT, Bernays S. Uneven stigma loads: Community interpretations of public health policies, 'evidence' and inequities in shaping Covid-19 stigma in Vietnam. *SSM Popul Health.* 2022;20:101270
18. World Health Organization. WHO handbook for guideline development [Internet]. 2nd ed. 2014 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241548960>
19. Norris SL. GRADE Good Practice Statements – A time to say “Good-bye”? A new typology for normative statements on interventions. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2024;171:111371
20. United Nations. Universal Declaration of Human Rights [Internet]. 1948 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>
21. World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Geneva [Internet]. 1948 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-geneva/>
22. The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights [Internet]. 1966 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>
23. World Health Organization, World Organization for Animal Health (OIE), Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). World Health Organization best practices for the naming of new human infectious diseases [Internet]. 2015 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-HSE-FOS-15.1>
24. World Health Organization. Guidance for managing ethical issues in infectious disease outbreaks [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241549837>
25. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights [Internet]. 2003 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.unesco.org/en/ethics-science-technology/bioethics-and-human-rights>

26. World Health Assembly. Framework on integrated, people-centred health services: report by the Secretariat. 2016 [cited 2025 July 23]; Available from: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/252698>
27. The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights [Internet]. 1966 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-economic-social-and-cultural-rights>
28. American Association for the International Commission of Jurists Siracusa Principles [Internet]. 1985. Available from: <https://www.icj.org/wp-content/uploads/1984/07/Siracusa-principles-ICCPR-legal-submission-1985-eng.pdf>
29. World Health Organization. Constitution of the World Health Organization [Internet]. 1948 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/about/governance/constitution>
30. International Center for Research on Women. Communities confront HIV stigma in Vietnam [Internet]. 2008 [cited 2025 July 23]. Available from: <https://www.icrw.org/publications/communities-confront-hiv-stigma-in-vietnam/>
31. Schünemann H, Brożek J, Guyatt G, Oxman A, editors. GRADE handbook for grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations [Internet]. Updated October 2013 [cited 2025 Aug 24]. Available from: <https://gdt.gradepro.org/app/handbook/handbook.html>
32. Driedger M, Mayhew A, Welch V, Agbata E, Gruner D, Greenaway C, et al. Accessibility and acceptability of infectious disease interventions among migrants in the EU/EEA: a CERQual systematic review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2018;15(11):2329
33. Nyblade L, Stockton MA, Giger K, Bond V, Ekstrand ML, Lean RM, et al. Stigma in health facilities: why it matters and how we can change it. *BMC Med*. 2019;17(1):25. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-019-1256-2>
34. Gronholm PC, Nosé M, van Brakel WH, Eaton J, Ebenso B, Fiekert K, et al. Reducing stigma and discrimination associated with COVID-19: early stage pandemic rapid review and practical recommendations. *Epidemiol Psychiatr Sci*. 2021;30:e15
35. Krameddine Y, DeMarco D, Hassel R, Silverstone PH. A novel training program for police officers that improves interactions with mentally ill individuals and is cost-effective. *Front Psychiatry*. 2013;4:9
36. Lamb D. Factors affecting the delivery of healthcare on a humanitarian operation in West Africa: A qualitative study. *Appl Nurs Res*. 2018;40:129–36
37. Collier KM, Klein EK, Sevalie S, Molleh B, Kabba Y, Kargbo A, et al. Ebola Virus Disease sensitization: community-driven efforts in Sierra Leone. *J Community Health*. 2024;49(1):108–16

38. Hartog K, Hubbard CD, Krouwer AF, Thornicroft G, Kohrt BA, Jordans MJD. Stigma reduction interventions for children and adolescents in low- and middle-income countries: Systematic review of intervention strategies. *Soc Sci Med*. 2020;246:112749
39. Kemp CG, Jarrett BA, Kwon CS, Song L, Jetté N, Sapag JC, et al. Implementation science and stigma reduction interventions in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *BMC Med*. 2019;17(1):6
40. WHO Centre for Human Development. MHPSS Interventions [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 1]. Available from: [https://wkc.who.int/our-work/health-emergencies/knowledge-hub/mental-health-psychosocial-support-\(mhpss\)/mhpss-interventions](https://wkc.who.int/our-work/health-emergencies/knowledge-hub/mental-health-psychosocial-support-(mhpss)/mhpss-interventions)
41. Techapoonpon K, Wonglertwisawakorn C, Kerdchareon N, Pruttithavorn W, Srikhamdokkhae O. Can a brief session of the online coronavirus disease 2019 destigmatization program reduce stigma among survivors? A randomized controlled trial. *Front Psychiatry*. 2023;14:1234038
42. Lu T, Guo Z, Li H, Zhang X, Ren Z, Yang W, et al. Effects of Wise Intervention on perceived discrimination among college students returning home from Wuhan during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Front Psychol*. 2021;12:689251
43. Sengupta S, Banks B, Jonas D, Miles MS, Smith GC. HIV interventions to reduce HIV/AIDS stigma: a systematic review. *AIDS Behav*. 2011;15(6):1075–87
44. Anindhita M, Haniifah M, Putri AMN, Karnasih A, Agiananda F, Yani FF, et al. Community-based psychosocial support interventions to reduce stigma and improve mental health of people with infectious diseases: a scoping review. *Infect Dis Poverty*. 2024;13(1):90
45. Fisher S, Kabir B, Lahiff E, MacLachlan M. Knowledge, attitudes, practices and implications of safe water management and good hygiene in rural Bangladesh: assessing the impact and scope of the BRAC WASH programme. *J Water Health*. 2011;9(1):80–93
46. Hofstraat K, van Brakel WH. Social stigma towards neglected tropical diseases: a systematic review. *Int Health*. 2016;8 Suppl 1:i53-70
47. Rao D, Elshafei A, Nguyen M, Hatzenbuehler ML, Frey S, Go VF. a systematic review of multi-level stigma interventions: state of the science and future directions. *BMC Med*. 2019;17(1):41
48. Parveen S, Islam MS, Begum M, Alam MU, Sazzad HMS, Sultana R, et al. It's not only what you say, it's also how you say it: communicating Nipah virus prevention messages during an outbreak in Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health*. 2016;16(1):726
49. Cascone S. Artist outfits Ebola PPE suits with photographs [Internet]. *Artnet News*. 2015 [cited 2025 Aug 1]. Available from: <https://news.artnet.com/art-world/artist-outfits-ebola-ppe-suits-286959>
50. Diniz D, Gumieri S, Bevilacqua BG, Cook RJ, Dickens BM. Zika virus infection in Brazil and human rights obligations. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*. 2017;136(1):105–10

51. Musoke D, Atusingwize E, Robins A, Nam S, Bonwitt J, Msukwa C, et al. Barriers to community engagement during the response to an Ebola virus disease outbreak in Uganda. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2025;10(3):e017285. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC11904350/>
52. Islam A, Pakrashi D, Vlassopoulos M, Wang LC. Stigma and misconceptions in the time of the COVID-19 pandemic: A Field Experiment in India *Soc Sci Med*. 2021;278:113966
53. Valeri L, Amsalem D, Jankowski S, Susser E, Dixon L. Effectiveness of a video-based intervention on reducing perceptions of fear, loneliness, and public stigma related to COVID-19: A randomized controlled trial. *Int J Public Health*. 2021;66:1604164
54. Crea TM, Collier KM, Klein EK, Sevalie S, Molleh B, Kabba Y, et al. Social distancing, community stigma, and implications for psychological distress in the aftermath of Ebola virus disease. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(11):e0276790
55. Stangl AL, Atkins K, Leddy AM, Sievwright KM, Sevelius JM, Lippman SA, et al. What do we know about interventions to reduce intersectional stigma and discrimination in the context of HIV? A systematic review. *Stigma and Health*. 2023;8(3):393–408
56. Zalwango MG, Paige S, Migisha R, Nakafeero Simbwa B, Nsubuga EJ, Asio A, et al. Stigma among Ebola disease survivors in Mubende and Kassanda districts, Central Uganda, 2022. *PLOS Glob Public Health*. 2024;4(12):e0003272
57. Person B, Sy F, Holton K, Govert B, Liang A, Garza B, et al. Fear and Stigma: The epidemic within the SARS outbreak. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2004;10(2):358–63
58. Pettigrew TF, Tropp LR. A meta-analytic test of intergroup contact theory. *J Pers Soc Psychol*. 2006;90(5):751–783
59. Stangl AL, Lloyd JK, Brady LM, Holland CE, Baral S. A systematic review of interventions to reduce HIV-related stigma and discrimination from 2002 to 2013: how far have we come? *J Int AIDS Soc*. 2013;16(3 Suppl 2):18734
60. Biesty CP, Hemingway C, Woolgar J, Taylor K, Lawton MD, Waheed MW, et al. Community led health promotion to counter stigma and increase trust amongst priority populations: lessons from the 2022–2023 UK mpox outbreak. *BMC Public Health*. 2024;24(1):1638
61. Nyarko Y, Goldfrank L, Ogedegbe G, Soghoian S, de-Graft Aikins A. Preparing for Ebola Virus Disease in West African countries not yet affected: perspectives from Ghanaian health professionals. *Global Health*. 2015;11:7
62. Keita M, Polonsky JA, Ahuka-Mundeke S, Ilumbulumbu MK, Dakissaga A, Boiro H, et al. A community-based contact isolation strategy to reduce the spread of Ebola virus disease: an analysis of the 2018–2020 outbreak in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2023;8(6):e011907

63. Siu JY. The SARS-associated stigma of SARS victims in the post-SARS era of Hong Kong. *Qual Health Res.* 2008;18(6):729–38
64. Majeed T, Hopkin G, Wang K, Nepal S, Votruba N, Gronholm P, et al. Anti-stigma interventions in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *eClinicalMedicine.* 2024;72:102612
65. Ford CL, Amani B, Harawa NT, Akee R, Gee GC, Sarrafzadeh M, et al. Adequacy of existing surveillance systems to monitor racism, social stigma and COVID inequities: a detailed assessment and recommendations. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18(24):13099

